

ISic2955

Small altar of Zeus Soter Hieron

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in excavation in Giardino Spagna (1948), area of the modern Umberto I hospital, Siracusa

Coordinates

37.074500, 15.282107

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 51593

Physical Description

A small horned altar of limestone, damaged across the top from front to back between the horns. The altar has mouldings around the base and the top on all four sides, with a smooth field in between on all four faces

Dimensions

Height 7 cm

Width 9.4 cm

Depth 4.5 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek text in the field on the front face of the altar (8.5 cm wide x 2.5 cm high)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The first three letters are more deeply engraved, the remaining letters are little more than scratched in the surface with a sharp point, and are increasingly irregular in form. Omega is open; top and bottom bars of sigma tending slightly apart; omicron is small than other letters; epsilon has horizontals of equal length.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 5-10 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Διὸς Σωτῆ
2. ρος Ἰέρωνος

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Altar of Zeus Soter of Hieron / Altar of Zeus Soter (dedicated by) Hieron / Altar of Zeus Soter Hieron

Commentary

Interpretation of this small altar is difficult and important. Small domestic altars of this sort are common, with the name of the divinity to which it is dedicated often in the genitive. The combination of Zeus Soter (Zeus the Saviour, a common form of Zeus; pot sherd graffiti on display in the same gallery as this altar in the Siracusa Archaeological museum attest to the existence of Zeus Soter cult in Hellenistic Syracuse; also possibly attested at Megara Hyblaea (Treziny 2018: 221 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/isicily/items/5UHWUE4K>])) together with the name Hieron encourages the idea that this altar reflects the existence of a ruler cult for Hieron II of Syracuse, with Hieron assimilated to Zeus Soter. The form of the letters is compatible with a third-century date. However, the presence of all three words in the genitive in this way is not typical and is awkward grammatically and lacks easy parallels. Additionally, there is no evidence for official ruler cult for Hieron II of Syracuse (see the extensive discussion in Habicht 1970 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/GBTECBTE>] and Serrati 2008 [<https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/items/RGWRF6PT>] in particular). The nature of the object (small domestic altar) together with the rather crude form of the inscription both suggest a private domestic context; however, the existence of such private veneration would more commonly be assumed on the basis of public cult.

Digital identifiers:

TM 284604

EDR 114491

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Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014